

Angelo Leogrande¹

Turnover from Innovative Products in Europe

It increased by 2.15% between 2014 and 2021

The European Innovation Scoreboard calculates the value of turnover from new products or significantly improved products on the total value of the overall turnover. This indicator is then used to calculate the value in terms of turnover of technological innovations.

JEL CODE: O30; O31, O32; O33; O36.

Keywords: Innovation, and Invention: Processes and Incentives; Management of Technological Innovation and R&D; Diffusion Processes; Open Innovation.

Ranking of European countries by value of turnover deriving from innovative or significantly improved products in 2021. Greece ranks first in value of turnover deriving from innovative or significantly improved products in 2021 with a value of 191.31 units, followed by Italy with an amount equal to 131.87 and from Spain with an amount equal to 125.50 units. In the middle of the table there are Slovakia with an amount equal to 83.60 units, followed by Ireland with a value of 77.93 units and Turkey with an amount equal to 73.31 units. North Macedonia closes the ranking with a value of 17.96 units, followed by Ukraine with an amount of 16.05 units and Denmark with a value of 0.00 units. On average, the value of the turnover deriving from innovative and significantly improved products in 2021 is equal to 79.37 units.

Ranking of countries by value of the percentage change in turnover deriving from innovative products between 2014 and 2021. Romania ranks first in terms of the percentage change in turnover deriving from innovative products between 2014 and 2021 with a value of 224.97% equal to an amount of 43.59 units, followed by Sweden with an amount equal to 161.63% equal to a value of 64.68 units, followed by Greece with a value equal to 116.74% equal to a amount of 103.4 units. In the middle of the table there are the United Kingdom with an amount of 11.06% equal to an amount of 12 units, followed by Poland with a value of 2.14% equal to an amount of 0.9 units, and by Cyprus equal to a value of 1.69% equal to an amount of 1.44 units. Ireland closes the ranking with a value of the percentage change in turnover deriving from innovative products between 2014 and 2021 equal to an amount of -59.26% equal to an amount equal to -113.37 units, followed by Turkey with a value equal to -61.68% equal to an amount of -118 units, and from Denmark with a value equal to -100.00% equal to an amount of 106.35%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering model is created below using the k-Means algorithm. The algorithm is optimized using the Silhouette coefficient. The result is therefore a two-way clustering system as indicated below, that is:

- *Cluster 1:* Poland, Montenegro, Norway, Sweden, Iceland, Latvia, Luxembourg, Bulgaria, Croatia, Romania, Malta, Bosnia, North Macedonia, Ukraine, Serbia, Estonia, Portugal,

¹ Ph.D. , Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia, European Union. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it

Cyprus, Lithuania, Finland, Hungary, Denmark, Slovenia, Belgium, Italy, Netherlands, Austria;

- *Cluster 2*: Slovakia, Switzerland, Ireland, Turkey, United Kingdom, Spain, Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, France.

It therefore follows that by calculating the value of the median for each of the clusters it results that the value of the median for cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 65.29, while the value of the median for cluster 2 is equal to a value of 103.74. The ordering of the clusters is therefore made up of C2> C1. From a geographical point of view, it is therefore clear that the countries that have a high level of turnover deriving from technological innovation applied to products are the central countries of Europe added to Turkey, the countries connected to Germany, UK and Ireland.

Network Analysis. An analysis is carried out below using network analysis using the Manhattan distance. The network analysis shows the following metrics i.e.:

- Number of nodes equal to 37;
- Number of edges equal to 45;
- Average Degree equal to 2,432;
- Density 0.0675.

Specifically, there are four different links, namely:

- Malta-Croatia with a value of 0.37;
- Italy-Finland with a value of 0.66;
- Norway-Latvia with a value of 0.57;
- Ukraine-North Macedonia with a value of 0.27.

Machine Learning and Predictions. An analysis is carried out below using a comparison between eight different machine learning algorithms for predicting the future value of the amount of turnover deriving from product innovation. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the data while the remaining 30% of the data was used for actual prediction. The algorithms have been classified based on their ability to maximize the R^2 and minimize three different types of statistical errors, namely "*Mean Absolute Error*", "*Mean Squared Error*", "*Root Mean Squared Error*". Following the performance analysis, the following payoffs were created, namely:

- *Linear Regression* with a payoff value of 9;
- *Gradient Boosted Tree* with a payoff value of 10
- *Simple Regression Tree* and PNN with a payoff value of 11;
- *Polynomial Regression* with a payoff value of 19;
- *ANN-Artificial Neural Network* with a payoff value of 24;
- *Tree Ensemble Regression* with a payoff value of 25;
- *Random Forest Regression* with a payoff value of 32.

It therefore follows that the best performing algorithm is Linear Regression. By applying Linear Regression, it is possible to identify the following predictions:

- *Czech Republic* with a decrease from an amount of 97.20 units up to a value of 85.47 units or equal to a variation of -11.73 units equal to a value of -12.07%;
- *Greece* with a decrease from an amount of 191.31 units up to a value of 110.79 units or equal to a variation of -80.52 units equal to an amount of -42.09%;
- *Spain* with a decrease from an amount of 125.51 units up to a value of 122.16 units or equal to an amount of -3.34 units equal to a value of -2.66%;

- *Finland* with a decrease from an amount of 109.91 units up to a value of 77.43 units or equal to a variation of -32.47 units equal to a value of -29.54%;
- *Italy* with a decrease from an amount equal to 131.87 units up to a value of 84.84 units or equal to a variation of -47.03 units equal to a value of -35.67%;
- *Latvia* with an increase from an amount of 59.40 units up to a value of 69.25 units or equal to a value of 9.85 units equal to a value of 16.58%;
- *Malta* with a decrease from an amount of 68.65 units up to a value of 57.96 units or equal to a variation of -10.69 units equal to a value of -15.58%;
- *Norway* with an increase from an amount of 56.56 units up to a value of 64.90 units or equal to a value of 8.33 units equal to a value of 14.73%;
- *Poland* with an increase from an amount of 42.80 units up to a value of 56.68 units equal to a variation of 13.88 units equal to a value of 32.43%;
- *Romania* with a decrease from an amount of 62.97 units up to a value of 53.56 units or equal to a variation of -9.41 units equal to a value of -14.95%;
- *Serbia* with a decrease from an amount of 88.94 units up to a value of 87.06 units equal to a variation of -1.89 units equal to a value of -2.12%;
- *Slovakia* with an increase from an amount of 83.60 units up to a value of 117.80 units or equal to a variation of 34.20 units equal to an amount of 40.91%.

On average, the value of the turnover deriving from innovative products is predicted to decrease from an amount of 93.23 units up to a value of 82.32 or equal to a variation of -10.90 units equal to a variation of -11.69 %.

Conclusions. The value of the turnover deriving from innovative or significantly improved products on average for the 37 European countries considered in the period between 2014 and 2021 grew by an amount equal to 2.15% equal to an amount of 1.67 units. Technological innovation can increase the profitability of companies. Businesses should invest in technological innovation to improve profit. However, some companies are too small to invest in technological innovation and research and development. Economic policies should create public and collaborative structures between the public and the private sector capable of generating innovation for SMEs. The creation of organizations oriented towards open innovation capable of increasing internal knowledge through external knowledge, with the possibility of crowd innovation, can further increase the value of the profit generated in connection with innovative products.

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Appendix with Econometrics and Statistical Results

Graph-level indices	Node-level indices
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Number of nodes	37
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Number of edges	45
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Average degree	2.432
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Density	0.06757
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Diameter	inf
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Radius	inf
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Average shortest path length	inf
<input type="checkbox"/> Number of strongly connected components	

2021	Country	Cluster	Silhouette
115.42	Austria	C1	0.593685
65.2903	Bosnia and Her...	C1	0.678091
121.594	Belgium	C1	0.610706
42.051	Bulgaria	C1	0.687251
86.683	Cyprus	C1	0.643625
0	Denmark	C1	0.630531
100.269	Estonia	C1	0.658837
109.905	Finland	C1	0.636148
85.8267	Croatia	C1	0.68206
63.3509	Hungary	C1	0.639877
35.3279	Iceland	C1	0.69146
131.87	Italy	C1	0.610864
68.933	Lithuania	C1	0.635926
42.0868	Luxembourg	C1	0.686762
59.3989	Latvia	C1	0.690605
49.0164	Montenegro	C1	0.693979
17.9646	North Macedonia	C1	0.676552
68.6489	Malta	C1	0.678791
57.9805	Netherlands	C1	0.609109
56.5637	Norway	C1	0.692545
42.8018	Poland	C1	0.694076
92.3247	Portugal	C1	0.647361
62.9692	Romania	C1	0.681759
88.9419	Serbia	C1	0.669989
104.692	Sweden	C1	0.691839
92.9525	Slovenia	C1	0.624338
16.0471	Ukraine	C1	0.676262
110.298	Switzerland	C2	0.656838
97.1946	Czechia	C2	0.569333
114.617	Germany	C2	0.552299
191.307	Greece	C2	0.546191
125.505	Spain	C2	0.639624
63.3632	France	C2	0.504289
77.9337	Ireland	C2	0.649807
83.5966	Slovakia	C2	0.664426
73.3086	Turkey	C2	0.643125
120.513	United Kingdom	C2	0.641789

Clusterization: C2>C1

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	Greece	191,31	20	Turkey	73,31
2	Italy	131,87	21	Lithuania	68,93
3	Spain	125,50	22	Malta	68,65
4	Belgium	121,59	23	Bosnia and Herzegovina	65,29
5	United Kingdom	120,51	24	France	63,36
6	Austria	115,42	25	Hungary	63,35
7	Germany	114,62	26	Romania	62,97
8	Switzerland	110,30	27	Latvia	59,40
9	Finland	109,90	28	Netherlands	57,98
10	Sweden	104,69	29	Norway	56,56
11	Estonia	100,27	30	Montenegro	49,02
12	Czechia	97,19	31	Poland	42,80
13	Slovenia	92,95	32	Luxembourg	42,09
14	Portugal	92,32	33	Bulgaria	42,05
15	Serbia	88,94	34	Iceland	35,33
16	Cyprus	86,68	35	North Macedonia	17,96
17	Croatia	85,83	36	Ukraine	16,05
18	Slovakia	83,60	37	Denmark	0,00
19	Ireland	77,93			

Variazione del Valore delle Vendite in Connessione a Prodotti Innovativi tra il 2014 ed il 2021.						
Ranl	Country	Var As	Var Pe	Rank	Country	Var Ass Var Per
1	Romania	43,59	225	20	Cyprus	1,44 1,69
2	Sweden	64,68	161,6	21	Bosnia and Herzegovina	0 0
3	Greece	103	116,7	22	Iceland	0 0
4	Lithuania	34,34	99,29	23	Montenegro	0 0
5	Latvia	28,68	93,39	24	North Macedonia	0 0
6	Estonia	45,75	83,9	25	Portugal	-1,64 -1,74
7	Norway	24,44	76,08	26	Czechia	-5,09 -4,98
8	Bulgaria	18,12	75,75	27	Malta	-6,2 -8,29
9	Italy	50,18	61,43	28	Hungary	-7,71 -10,85
10	Austria	43,45	60,37	29	Ukraine	-4,27 -21,02
11	Serbia	33,24	59,67	30	Luxembourg	-13,47 -24,25
12	Belgium	36,21	42,41	31	Switzerland	-45,21 -29,07
13	Finland	26,9	32,42	32	Netherlands	-31,04 -34,87
14	Slovenia	15,01	19,26	33	France	-39,62 -38,47
15	Croatia	12,49	17,03	34	Slovakia	-71,79 -46,2
16	Germany	15,94	16,15	35	Ireland	-113,4 -59,26
17	Spain	15,18	13,76	36	Turkey	-118 -61,68
18	United Kingdom	12	11,06	37	Denmark	-106,4 -100
19	Poland	0,9	2,14			

Performance degli Algoritmi						
R	Algoritmo	R^2	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error	Totale
1	Linear Regression	3	2	2	2	9
2	Gradient Boosted Tree	5	3	1	1	10
3	Simple Regression Tree	1	4	3	3	11
4	PNN	2	1	4	4	11
5	Polynomial Regression	4	5	5	5	19
6	ANN	6	7	4	7	24
7	Tree Ensemble Regression	7	6	6	6	25
8	Random Forest Regression	8	8	8	8	32

Country	2021	Prediction	Var Ass	Var Perc
<i>Repubblica Ceca</i>	★ 97,20	★ 85,47	★ -11,73	★ -12,07
<i>Grecia</i>	★ 191,31	★ 110,79	★ -80,52	★ -42,09
<i>Spagna</i>	★ 125,51	★ 122,16	★ -3,34	★ -2,66
<i>Finlandia</i>	★ 109,91	★ 77,43	★ -32,47	★ -29,54
<i>Italia</i>	★ 131,87	★ 84,84	★ -47,03	★ -35,67
<i>Lettonia</i>	★ 59,40	★ 69,25	★ 9,85	★ 16,58
<i>Malta</i>	★ 68,65	★ 57,96	★ -10,69	★ -15,58
<i>Norvegia</i>	★ 56,56	★ 64,90	★ 8,33	★ 14,73
<i>Polonia</i>	★ 42,80	★ 56,68	★ 13,88	★ 32,43
<i>Romania</i>	★ 62,97	★ 53,56	★ -9,41	★ -14,95
<i>Serbia</i>	★ 88,94	★ 87,06	★ -1,89	★ -2,12
<i>Slovakia</i>	★ 83,60	★ 117,80	★ 34,20	★ 40,91
<i>Media</i>	★ 93,23	★ 82,32	★ -10,90	★ -11,69